

DEVELOPMENT OF MEDICINE IN UZBEKISTAN DURING THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE. THE MAIN ACHIEVEMENTS IN THE MEDICINE OF THE NEW UZBEKISTAN.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6602373>

Khidirov Lazizbek Azizovich

*Samarkand State Medical University
Faculty of Pediatrics, 1st year student*

Oblanova Dinara Sirojiddinovna

*Samarkand State Medical University
Faculty of Pediatrics, 3rd year student*

Scientific adviser: Tursunova Gavhar Begmurodovna

Annotation: *The importance of general medicine in the life of the organism, the interdependence of medicine on the way of life of the organism and the changes and achievements in pre-independence and post-independence medicine of Uzbekistan, as well as world medicine and Uzbek medicine. is to study, albeit in part, the shortcomings between them by comparison.*

Keywords: *Epidemic, hospital, parasitology, immunobiology, patient, resuscitation.*

The article partially describes the pre-independence medicine of Uzbekistan, the current state of medicine in Uzbekistan is interpreted on the basis of the source, and its specific directions are applied.

Introduction. During the former Soviet colonial period, significant changes were made in the field of medicine in Uzbekistan. In the 20s of the last century, a number of organizational work was done in this direction. The People's Commissariat of Health was established and the existing hospitals, dispensaries and other medical facilities in the country were transferred to the state. Mobile teams have been set up to treat and fight epidemics, a bacteriological laboratory has been launched, and a total of 7,000 hospitals have been opened. Diseases such as smallpox, plague, ringworm, malaria, trachoma, leishmaniasis have been largely eliminated in the country, while tuberculosis, skin diseases and other diseases have been significantly reduced.

The material and technical base of the medical system in the country has been gradually expanded and strengthened. In large hospitals in Tashkent, specialized departments of ophthalmology, ear, neurology and other similar departments

have been established. A new hospital has been opened in Samarkand, a children's hospital in Kokand, and a special hospital in Fergana that treats patients with physiotherapeutic methods. In Tashkent on the basis of a small private hospital in this area in 1919 was established Institute of Physiotherapy for 150 beds.

In 1920, the first tuberculosis dispensary was opened in Tashkent. In 1922, the organization of medical and sanitary control was established. In 1924, a dispensary for skin and genital diseases was opened in Tashkent, and a tropical medical institute (now the Scientific Research Institute of Medical Parasitology in Samarkand) was opened in Bukhara. By 1924, Turkestan had 6 tropical stations and their local networks. In 1924, there were 53 hospitals, 151 outpatient clinics (79 of them in rural areas), 40 paramedic stations and other institutions in the republic. During these years, medical education and training of medical specialists from the local population began. In 1918, the first medical school in Tashkent - now the Republican Medical School named after Akhunbabayev - was opened, and a year later, a higher medical school was opened, paramedic and short-term surgical courses were organized. In 1920, the Higher School of Medicine was transformed into a medical faculty within the Central Asian State University. In order to prepare young people to study at this faculty, working faculties were opened in many cities of the republic, which attracted Uzbek and other local youth. Central Asian State University has played an important role not only in the training of medical personnel with higher education, but also in the opening of new medical schools on the ground. In 1931, the medical faculty of the university was transformed into an independent medical institute (Tashkent Medical Institute). Samarkand Medical Institute was opened in Samarkand. In 1932, the Tashkent Institute of Postgraduate Medical Education was established. In 1937, the Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute began its work. At the same time, research institutes were established. In 1937 there were tuberculosis institutes in Tashkent, in 1940 there were blood transfusion institutes. Many doctors were sent to industrial enterprises and rural areas, new hospitals, clinics, dispensaries were opened in cities and villages, climatic resorts and hospitals were built in clean and pleasant places.

During the war of 1941-45, the medical system of Uzbekistan had a very responsible task. It was necessary to open hospitals for wounded and wounded fighters, to further strengthen the material and technical base, to maintain a stable sanitary condition of the country. More than 130 military hospitals were soon opened. Special surgical hospitals have been opened in the country to treat war invalids.

Although the medical network has expanded considerably during this period, there has been an increase in various internal diseases among the population as a result of environmental imbalances such as environmental degradation, in particular the introduction of various strong chemicals, cotton monopoly and other social ills.

By the end of the twentieth century and the beginning of the twenty-first century, world medicine has reached a new stage in its development. This rise was due to the social, economic and cultural changes that took place around the world. These changes first appeared as a result of the modern scientific and technological revolution. The technical advances of the twentieth century have risen to such an extent that even the human foot has reached the moon. The rise has spread to all areas of human life, including medicine. Previously unknown methods of diagnosis, treatment and prevention have been developed in this area. The latest advances in science and technology have been used for these purposes. For example, radium and laser beams, sophisticated laboratory testing methods have been introduced. Immunobiological processes were studied. As a result, it was possible to perform a method of replacing the heart, kidneys and other organs that became disabled due to the disease. In some countries, for example, in our country, some diseases that were previously common (malaria, measles, mumps, polio, diphtheria) have been terminated as a nosological form. Scientists have done a great deal of research in the field of medicine and have solved many problems. However, along with these successes, new challenges also emerged. Modern scientific and technological advances have led to the use of various chemicals in agriculture and industry, the exploration of space, the use of radioactive substances and nuclear energy, and finally the many tests of atomic bombs on the atmosphere, the earth's ability to water bodies are polluted, damaging the health of people and all living things. Thus, very responsible and complex problems have arisen in the face of modern world medicine.

After gaining independence, the republic began a period of recovery in all spheres of political, economic and cultural life, including medicine. Measures have been developed to radically improve health care. On August 26, 1996, a special State Law "On Health Care of Citizens of Uzbekistan" was adopted. In this regard, the following three important issues of state importance have been legislated: 1) ensuring the state's guarantee of the rights of citizens to health care; 2) formation of a healthy lifestyle of citizens; 3) legal determination of the activities of all state and public organizations in the country in the field of public health.

The Law on Health sets out the basic rules for public health. These rules include: 1) observance of human rights in the field of health care; 2) all segments of the population have access to medical care; 3) priority of preventive measures; 4) social protection of citizens who have lost their health; 5) unity of medical sciences with practice. The law also defines the structure and powers of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The second important step in the health sector after Uzbekistan's independence was the reform of the health care system. The President issued a special decree on this. In accordance with this decree, health professionals, scientists, lawyers and organizations responsible for this work have developed a program of reforming the health care system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In order to raise the level of the ambulance system to a higher level, the program envisages the establishment of the Republican Emergency Medical Center and its regional branches on the basis of a number of medical institutions (Tashkent city ambulance department, Republican and Tashkent regional air ambulance). According to the decree, it is planned to establish faculties for the training of highly qualified medical nurses (resuscitators, obstetricians) at higher medical schools for a period of three years.

The quality and effectiveness of medical care depends on the experience of medical staff. With this in mind, special attention has been paid in our country to the training of experienced doctors with advanced knowledge.

After gaining independence, there have been dramatic positive changes in the field of higher medical education. Our medical schools have the opportunity to directly communicate and exchange experiences with leading medical training centers abroad. At the initiative of President Islam Karimov, many students, graduate students and researchers have been sent to foreign universities. These measures have borne fruit, the teaching and educational work in our universities has significantly increased, and they have approached the level of world universities.

In order to provide the necessary funds for the implementation of measures to reform and improve the health care system in the country, the Cabinet of Ministers on December 2, 1997 decided. In addition to the funds allocated by the government, the resolution provides for the use of investments from various charities, foreign investments and commercial institutions, in which part of the cost of treatment is borne by patients. From January, patients were paid to eat during their treatment in hospitals. In addition, various non-governmental funds have been established to provide additional funding to the health care

system. As a result of these measures, some positive results have been achieved in the reform and improvement of health care in the Republic.

On February 26, 2003, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further reform the health care system" was issued. It is envisaged to carry out deeper and broader reforms in the healthcare system in the country, the formation of specialized medical centers of high world standards, the introduction of advanced medical technologies, the creation of financial, economic and legal conditions. . In particular, it is planned to establish special clinics and medical centers equipped with modern diagnostic and treatment equipment. For example, specialized centers for urology, surgery, eye microsurgery, and specialized cardiology will be established in the country. These institutions train well-trained medical professionals. They improve their skills in highly clinically advanced foreign clinics.

All the measures listed above are the first step towards the development of medical science and healthcare in our country.

REFERENCES:

1. A.A.Qodirov History of medicine. Tashkent-2005, "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan", State Scientific Publishing House.
2. F.R.Borodulin History of Medicine, Collection of Lectures. Moscow "Medicine", 1961
3. P.E.Zabludovskiy History of Medicine, Collection of Lectures. Moscow "Medicine", 1981
4. T.G.Begmurodovna RESETTLEMENT AND LIVING CONDITIONS OF THE POPULATION EVACUATED FROM RUSSIA TO THE SYRDARYA (SECOND HALF OF THE XIX CENTURY) //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. - 2022. - T.3. - №.3. - C. 800-803.
5. G.B.Tursunova Tibbiyotda ma'naviyat masalalari, shifokor ma'naviyati //Science and Education. - 2021. - T.2. - №.5. - C. 790-793.